

Paper 3**PERSON CENTERED APPROACH FOR ADULTS WITH INTELLECTUAL CHALLENGES: A CASE STUDY OF DIYA FOUNDATION****B. Preethi Meena¹, Suphala S Kotian² & Jerusha Susan Thomas³**¹Research scholar, Srinivas University, Mangalore, India

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ABSTRACT

This paper is a case study of a non governmental organization based in Bangalore which provides vocational training to adults with intellectual challenges. People with intellectual challenges are those who face difficulty in intellectual functioning and adaptation. A study was conducted to understand the effect of vocational training for Persons with Intellectual disabilities, the post results showed that the participants were able to retain the employment and be self dependent[1]. Diya Foundation is one such vocational training center which provides training on Daily living skills, Personal social skills and Employability skills for adults with intellectual challenges. This organization was started by Mrs. Maria S Santamaria. A special educator by profession, she has a Masters in Special Education from Cardinal Stritch College, and her work experience in job coaching uniquely equipped her to start a Vocational Training Center for adults with intellectual challenges.

Keywords: - NGO, Children with Intellectual challenges, Adults with intellectual challenges, Mothers, Trainers, Therapies, Direct support services.

1. INTRODUCTION:

Intellectual disability is defined by the significant limitations to cognitive and adaptive function [2]. Adults with intellectual challenges have a huge potential to be self-dependent and productive provided their training is structured and systematic. One way of looking at disability as per the Indian context is on factors such as cultural, social aspects and address the differences [3]. The Vocational Rehabilitation and Employment (Disabled Persons) Convention states that there should be equal treatment of non disabled and disabled persons. [4].The perspective of disability is evolving and will be more meaningful if the involvement of parents increases[5]. In developing countries like India disability is a public health concern for which many professionals in the disability sector require ethical practice [6]. In the last 23 years Diya has impacted over 200 adults with intellectual challenges and made life altering changes in over 800 lives. These adults have had life altering changes in their self esteem, self dependence and productivity through systematic and consistent training in the Diya training program. They have learnt skills like personal grooming and hygiene, household and financial management, personal social skills, occupational guidance and employability skills. Economic participation is one such

meaningful aspect of inclusion [7]. Exclusion can be of any form such as inaccessible spaces, poor training facilities, lack of trained professionals, not advocating for the needy etc. [8]. Vocational training acts as a medium to bridge the gap between neurotypical and neurodiverse individuals [9]. Diya provides adults and young adults facing intellectual challenges and disabilities with vocational and life skills, making them employment-ready. They equip them to become valuable contributors to society.

2. VISION:

To see individuals with a disability and their families become alive with dignity and pride in the present and operating with love, respect and confidence for the future.

3. MISSION:

To enrich the quality of life and bring dignity to differently abled adults by educating them in life skills and employability skills towards self-dependence, building support systems and enhancing awareness in the Community.

4. GOAL:

Goal is to help women and men with intellectual disabilities to become industry-ready and earning members of society who lead self-reliant and dignified lives.

5. ORGANIZATION STRUCTURE:

This organization is led by Maria S. Santamaria, CEO and Founder of Diya Foundation. The organization holds a group of experienced professionals over more than 10 years in the organization. The team has over 15 staff members out of which some are on contract or part time basis. There are 5 Person centered trainers and 3 Project leaders. Diya has expanded their expertise in different fields and thus they have another manager who is managing short term courses and NGO Capacity building collaborations. There is a program coordinator who manages all this reporting to the CEO.

6. HISTORY:

The organization was started by Ms. Maria - popularly known as Sarah. A special educator by profession, she has a Masters in Special Education from Cardinal Stritch College, and her work experience in job coaching uniquely equipped her to start a Vocational Training Center for adults with intellectual challenges and led to her founding Diya Foundation in 1999. These are some of our milestones: through the 23 years, as their Vision and Mission became clearer and their team grew together they were able to expand from just being a Sheltered Workshop to much more as the team built each other up to support and deliver on their Vision. The number of students and staff has increased with the fine tuning of various projects which began with a view to building the all-round capacity of our students and this in turn led to many new collaborations and enhanced networking with like-minded individuals.

7. CURRENT PROJECTS:

Currently, they follow a person-centered approach. This means that any adult who walks in is involved in helping them understand their achievements and skills they have achieved thus far

and then involved in setting up his / her future goals. These goals are in sync with their strengths, skills and dreams and are also aligned with their parents and family expectations which involves their commitment. The students are taken on a journey of discovery to build up their capacity to the maximum extent possible to make themselves independent and earning/contributing members.

1. **Daily living Skills:** Adaptive functioning, or an individual's ability to care for self and function independently is a primary consideration when supporting individuals with autism and other disabilities. Daily living skills, also referred to as activities of daily living (ADLs), are routine, self-care tasks in which most people participate on a daily basis without assistance. Life skills are considered the fuel that powers life; without the ability to survive and thrive, it would be difficult to lead a productive life.
2. **Personal Social Skills:** Sessions on setting daily routines, provided behavioral therapy activities, art therapy and role play therapy to help manage emotions, increase self awareness and improve social skills. These sessions proved to be very beneficial as remarkable changes were noticed in Trainees. Parents were able to bring in routines that helped their ward be actively engaged, occupied and productive in meaningful ways. While some of them now support in household chores, others have learnt to make eye contact, communicate using facial expressions and smiles and some others are keen on learning new skills.
3. **Employability skills:** The students are being oriented and trained on team work, handling work pressure, attending online meetings with their supervisor, sharing their challenges, meeting the expectations of their clients, achieving deadlines and many more.
4. **Short term courses:** Apart from the main training, students are also undergoing short term courses such as Cooking class where they learn skills such as fireless cooking, learning process to cook, knife skills etc. Digitization is another course where they learn basic computer skills and get certified by DIYA. Physical fitness classes are also conducted to enhance stability and muscular strength of adults with intellectual challenges. Financial literacy is one such holistic project which creates a lot of impact in terms of teaching budgeting skills, community support, being a provider to their family etc.
5. **Therapies:** Adults with intellectual disabilities face difficulty in speech and physical endurance. To improve their speech and physical strength Diya is training them on speech therapy and physiotherapy. For those who enjoy art and express their feelings through art, Diya also provides art therapy as a medium of relief and expression.
6. **Employment:** Employing adults with intellectual disabilities across many sectors such as hospitality, housekeeping, IT, Food and Beverage etc. has been the end goal of Diya for their adults. Diya has tied up with companies and institutions for each of these sectors to initiate internship opportunities which will be converted to employment as a long term plan.

8. SWOT ANALYSIS:

SWOT analysis plays an important tool to analyze organization strategy planning [10].

(a) Strengths: Diya's strength comes from the collective collaboration of various stakeholders- namely, parents of our trainees, board members, corporates/volunteers, investors, trainers, staff, interns, volunteers etc. When the staff work in collaboration with the parents and the best interests of the student which is person centered, we see an effective outcome. Another aspect

is having potential employers willing to support and provide jobs that are feasible for our trainees. These jobs give a sense of inclusion and involvement.

(b) Weaknesses: Lack of effective communication between various stakeholders affects best practices within the organization. Other potential weak areas are parents not being cooperative with the plans shared or various job openings provided by companies who aren't sensitive to the students and their needs. Another weak area is not planning properly, when the sessions aren't being planned along with the required materials needed, the class is not as effective as it can be. When we don't keep a student at the center, we tend to be system centered following the system's practice and not what is best for each student.

(c) Opportunities: Possible opportunities could be working on various levels such as in education, rural development, environment, advocacy and research sectors. This will engage many persons with intellectual disabilities and their families towards a dignified life and access equal opportunities. Another possible opportunity is to continue the engagement of volunteering and internship for other stakeholders. Simultaneously build the capacity of parents and corporations for sustainable development. Other opportunities include collaborating with other companies to provide roles that students can fit in and work.

(d) Threats: With new CSR policies the corporate sector has tightened the process and are liable for every fund spent for a project. The organization should ensure that each project receives the funding on time and continue the effective utilization of funds.

9. ACTION PLAN:

Following are the action plan for Diya to ensure they continue their progress:

1. Engage professionals for implementation of projects and ensure the effective documentation of the projects.
2. Ensure online fundraising mediums or platforms are updated regularly for continued funding and supporting projects.
3. Build the database of as many CSR companies as possible other than the existing companies for future fundraising and grants.
4. Engage more parents or family members in the training programs so that the ecosystem is being built for improvement.
5. To build a collaborative work environment within Diya as well as with those they interact with-other stakeholders.
6. Document success stories, challenges, what works best and what doesn't work as it helps companies who provide funds and parents to see progress as well as understand reasons why a goal may not work.
7. Engage more volunteers as well as interns to help spread about inclusion of Pwds at workplaces.
8. To provide effective sensitization of different employees at different workplaces so that they understand their colleagues who have disabilities, can relate better to them and build a respectful relationship with them.

10. CONCLUSION

A study states that out of all disabilities, intellectual disability faces greater challenges [11]. Vocational training is always focused at building the skills of each adult in Diya Foundation and leading to an employment pathway. There is high job satisfaction found in employed persons with intellectual disabilities [12]. With inclusive education and providing accessible spaces and opportunities there will be a significant rise in employing persons with intellectual disabilities which will improve their self esteem and feel dignified in the society [13]. From the employer's perspective with organization changes and diversity and inclusion hiring there could be possible employment opportunities for adults with intellectual disabilities [14]. In India the employment placement of people with disabilities is comparatively less [15]. Over so many years Diya has focused on not only working with beneficiaries but also their family members. Working in collective helps in reaching greater milestones which is a best practice by Diya Foundation. Although there are laws advocating for disability and for people with disabilities, there is still a scope of implementing the policies in a worthwhile manner [16]. Employment and dignified life is one of the right of persons with intellectual disability which is as equal to any other person [17]. A study focused on in depth interviews of persons with intellectual challenges stated that the physical environment needed more inclusion practices [18]. There is a need for comprehensive rehabilitation structures for persons with disabilities which will uplift their life and self esteem [19]. Since people with intellectual disabilities come from rural and urban setting, the government should cater to the needs of each one of them and ensure they are aware of their rights and responsibilities thus resulting in dignified lives [20].

REFERENCES:

- [1] Nuri, M. R. P., et al, (2012). Impact assessment of a vocational training program for persons with disabilities in Bangladesh. *Disability, CBR & Inclusive Development*, 23(3), [Google scholar](#)↗
- [2] Chavan BS, Rozatkar AR. Intellectual disability in India: Charity to right based. *Indian J Psychiatry*. 2014 Apr;56(2):113-6. [Google Scholar](#)↗
- [3] Ghai, A. (2015). *Rethinking Disability in India* (1st ed.). Routledge India. [Google Scholar](#)↗
- Shenoy, M. (2011). Persons with disability and the India labour market: Challenges and opportunities. *ILO*, 13(1). [Google Scholar](#)↗
- [4] Girimaji, Satish C; Srinath, Shoba Perspectives of intellectual disability in India: epidemiology, policy, services for children and adults, *Current Opinion in Psychiatry*: September 2010 - Volume 23 - Issue 5 - p 441-446. [Google Scholar](#)↗
- [5] Kumar SG, Roy G, Kar SS. Disability and rehabilitation services in India: issues and challenges. *J Family Med Prim Care*. 2012 Jan;1(1):69-73. [Google Scholar](#)↗
- [6] Cobley, D. S. (2013). Towards economic participation: Examining the impact of the convention on the rights of persons with disabilities in India. *Disability & Society*, 28(4), 441-455. [Google Scholar](#)↗
- [7] Malle, A. Y., Pirttimaa, R., & Saloviita, T. (2015). Inclusion of students with disabilities in formal vocational education programs in Ethiopia. *International Journal of Special Education*, 30(2), 57-67. [Google Scholar](#)↗

- [8] Razzak, A., & Khaki, M. Z. (2015). Designing a Model of Vocational Training programs for Disables in Pakistan. The online journal of New Horizons in Education, 5(1), 27. [Google Scholar](#)
- [9] GURL, E. (2017). SWOT analysis: A theoretical review [Google Scholar](#)
- [10] Rao, L. G. (2008). Education of persons with intellectual disabilities in India. salud pública de méxico, 50, s205-s212. [Google Scholar](#)
- [11] Kocman, A., & Weber, G. (2018). Job satisfaction, quality of work life and work motivation in employees with intellectual disability: A systematic review. Journal of Applied Research in Intellectual Disabilities, 31(1), 1-22. [Google Scholar](#)
- [12] Moore, E. J., & Schelling, A. (2015). Postsecondary inclusion for individuals with an intellectual disability and its effects on employment. Journal of Intellectual Disabilities, 19(2), 130-148. [Google Scholar](#)
- [13] Kocman, A., Fischer, L., & Weber, G. (2018). The employers' perspective on barriers and facilitators to employment of people with intellectual disability: A differential mixed-method approach. Journal of Applied Research in Intellectual Disabilities, 31(1), 120-131. [Google Scholar](#)
- [14] Sophie Mitra, & Sambamoorthi, U. (2006). Employment of Persons with Disabilities: Evidence from the National Sample Survey. Economic and Political Weekly, 41(3), 199–203. [Google Scholar](#)
- [15] Mitra, S., & Sambamoorthi, U. (2006). Government programs to promote employment among persons with Disabilities in India. Mitra, S. and U. Sambamoorthi (2006), Government Programs to Promote Employment among Persons with Disabilities in India, Indian Journal of Social Development, 6(2), 195-213. [Google Scholar](#)
- [16] Elahdi, A., & Alnahdi, G. H. (2022). Factors associated with workers' attitudes towards employment of persons with intellectual disabilities in Saudi Arabia. Journal of Applied Research in Intellectual Disabilities, 35(3), 856-866. [Google Scholar](#)
- [17] Adhikari, E. R. (2018). The experiences of learners with disabilities in mainstream vocational training in Nepal. International journal for research in vocational education and training, 5(4), 307-327. [Google Scholar](#)
- [18] Hansen, C. H., Mahmud, I., & Bhuiyan, A. J. (2007). Vocational reintegration of people with spinal cord lesion in Bangladesh: an observational study based on a vocational training project at CRP. Asia Pacific Disability Rehabilitation Journal, 18(1), 63-75. [Google Scholar](#)
- [19] Narahariseti, R., & Castro, M. C. (2016). Factors associated with persons with disability employment in India: a cross-sectional study. BMC public health, 16(1), 1-8. [Google Scholar](#)